

Report

Mapping Repositories and their Institutional Open Science Policies in MENA

Mohamad Mostafa | Regional Engagement Specialist: Middle East & Asia

17 September 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11370031>

DataCite is a global community that shares a common interest: to ensure that research outputs and resources are openly available and connected so that their reuse can advance knowledge across and between disciplines, now and in the future. As a community, we make research more effective with metadata that connects research outputs and resources—from samples and images to data and preprints. We enable the creation and management of persistent identifiers (PIDs), integrate services to improve research workflows, and facilitate the discovery and reuse of research outputs and resources.

DataCite is registered as a non-profit organization in Hannover, Germany with a team distributed across the globe. For any questions or comments about the report please contact us at: support@datacite.org.

This report is part of DataCite's Global Access Program ([GAP](#)) activities. The program has been made possible in part by grant 2022-316573 from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative.

This report is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of the license, please check <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Cover image: [petra_shawarmaltdjordanian](#)

Infrastructure and Awareness Landscape Analysis in Middle East and North Africa (MENA)

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	5
1.1 Open Research and the Value of Open Infrastructure	5
1.2 Role of PIDs in Building a Trusted Research Infrastructure	5
1.3 DataCite Role in Building Sustainable Infrastructure	6
1.4 DataCite Global Access Program	7
2. Scope and Methodology	8
2.1 Aspect A: Infrastructure Landscape Analysis	10
2.2 Aspect B: Infrastructure awareness landscape analysis	12
3. Results and Discussions	13
Aspect A: Infrastructure Landscape Analysis in MENA	13
3.1 Existing Repositories & Systems in MENA	13
3.2 Repository Service Providers Landscape in MENA	20
3.3 Infrastructure Landscape Discussions	24
Aspect B: Awareness Landscape Analysis in MENA	25
3.4 Landscape of Open Access Repositories Institutional Policies (Source: ROARMAP)	25
3.5 Awareness Landscape Discussions	26
4. Conclusion	27
5. Funding Statement	28
6. Acknowledgments	28
7. Appendix: Glossary	28
8. References	29

Executive Summary

The utilization of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) has emerged as a fundamental building block for establishing a reliable and globally accessible research infrastructure. PIDs, such as the Digital Object Identifier (DOI), play a crucial role in ensuring the accessibility of all research outputs and resources, facilitating seamless attribution and communication in scholarly workflows. The Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region is producing a diverse array of research outputs in different languages, contributing to the global knowledge pool. Despite the rich scholarly outputs, the presence of MENA repositories in global aggregates and networks remains limited, preventing the region's research visibility and impact on the global stage. Moreover, the level of awareness about the important role of DOI and the adoption of open PIDs among research communities in the MENA region is low. This report highlights the current landscape of repository and scholarly infrastructure in MENA and the existing Open Science policies. Addressing the current gaps in PID adoption and awareness in MENA requires collaborative efforts among various stakeholders, including academic institutions, researchers, funders, and librarians, and governmental bodies, to promote the integration of open science policies and practices. This report is the first step towards better understanding how to support local communities in MENA to build a more open research infrastructure and promote Open Science practices.

1. Introduction

1.1 Open Research and the Value of Open Infrastructure

In the digital age, the landscape of scientific research and innovation is rapidly evolving, and Open Research has emerged as a transformative paradigm that holds immense promise for the advancement of scholarship and knowledge. Open Research represents a fundamental shift in the way research is conducted, shared, and accessed. At its core, Open Research advocates for the open and transparent dissemination of scientific knowledge, data, and methodologies, transcending traditional barriers and fostering collaboration among researchers, institutions, and the public at large. Central to the success of Open Science is the concept of Open Infrastructure, a critical component that underpins this revolutionary approach to scientific inquiry.

Open Infrastructure includes a wide array of digital tools, platforms, and resources designed to facilitate and support the principles of Open Science. These infrastructure elements encompass repositories, collaborative platforms, and open-source software, among others. They are the technological backbone that enables researchers to seamlessly share their research outputs, collaborate across borders, and harness the collective intelligence of the global scientific community. As such, Open Infrastructure is not only integral to the realization of Open Science goals but also contributes to the democratization of knowledge, accelerating the pace of discovery, and addressing pressing global challenges [1, 2].

1.2 Role of PIDs in Building a Trusted Research Infrastructure

PIDs are the backbone of building a trusted and sustainable research infrastructure in today's digital age [3]. They serve as unique, unchanging labels for digital objects, such as research papers, preprints, datasets, and even individual researchers, ensuring their enduring recognition, discoverability, and accessibility. PIDs play a pivotal role in enhancing the credibility and longevity of research assets while fostering transparency and trust within the scholarly ecosystem.

In the context of scholarly communication, PIDs offer numerous advantages. They enable accurate and reliable attribution of research contributions, ensuring that authors receive due credit for their work and allowing for the tracking of scholarly

impact over time. PIDs also facilitate effective data management and sharing by providing a stable reference for datasets, which is crucial for reproducibility and data citation. Also, they could help in saving the research sector money [4] and reducing researchers' wasted time in administrative tasks [5].

Moreover, PIDs enhance the discoverability of research outputs by connecting them across diverse platforms and repositories. This interconnectedness not only aids researchers in finding relevant resources but also promotes interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge integration. PIDs also contribute to the sustainability of research infrastructure by reducing the risk of link rot and ensuring that valuable research remains accessible for future generations.

PIDs empower researchers to navigate the vast landscape of digital information, promote open science practices, and safeguard the integrity and longevity of scholarly contributions. As research becomes increasingly reliant on digital resources, PIDs will continue to play a pivotal role in shaping the future of scholarly communication and knowledge dissemination.

1.3 DataCite Role in Building Sustainable Infrastructure

DataCite is a global community that shares a common interest: to ensure that research outputs and resources are openly available and connected so that their reuse can advance knowledge across and between disciplines, now and in the future. DataCite plays a vital role in building a sustainable and open research infrastructure by providing DOIs for various research outputs and resources such as datasets, preprints, theses, samples, etc. DOIs ensure the long-term attribution, accessibility, and recognition of outputs, a critical component of open science. We make research more effective by connecting research outputs and resources—from data and preprints to images and samples. We support the creation and management of DOIs and metadata records, enhance research workflows with service integration, and enable the discovery and reuse of research outputs and resources. In line with DataCite's vision of connecting research and advancing knowledge and as part of its multi-year strategic plan [6], we started to focus our efforts on exploring ways to remove access barriers and increase adoption and participation on a global scale.

1.4 DataCite Global Access Program

In 2023, DataCite launched a [Global Access Program \(GAP\)](#), an initiative to improve access and enable communities in lesser-represented regions to further benefit from our open infrastructure services [7]. The program has been made possible in part by grant 2022-316573 from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative. DataCite has taken a comprehensive approach to achieve this goal. The GAP is based on three pillars:

- **Outreach:**

In learning from local community stakeholders, we seek to increase awareness of PID infrastructure, establish a platform of collaborations, and build regional partnerships. Also, increasing our engagement efforts through various outreach activities such as webinars, workshops, and events.

- **Technical Infrastructure:**

By analyzing the infrastructure landscape and use of different platforms per region, we aim to better understand the opportunities and challenges for DataCite infrastructure adoption. We seek to collaborate with service providers on enabling integrations for certain regions and setting up user groups to benefit from each other's expertise and/or reuse code for integrations. Through partnerships with local and international stakeholders, the program will seek to support communities in building technical infrastructure per their needs (and design).

- **Funding:**

In 2023, DataCite launched the [Global Access Fund](#) (GAF) to provide financial support for both outreach activities and infrastructure development to enable organizations in GAP regions (Africa, Asia, Middle East, and Latin America) and communities. The GAF will allocate funding to projects in the scope of outreach and engagement activities, open Infrastructure development and integration, and demonstrators that can make a broader impact on a national or regional level. Around 185 applications have been received from Africa, Asia, Middle East and Latin America and [12 institutions](#) from Lebanon, Mexico, Uganda, India, Argentina, Côte d'Ivoire, Zimbabwe, Indonesia, Georgia, Tunisia, Nigeria, and Brazil have been awarded the fund [8].

2. Scope and Methodology

This report delves into the MENA region's research landscape to gain deeper insights into the underlying research infrastructure. Covering two major aspects, the report focuses on A) Infrastructure landscape analysis and B) Awareness landscape analysis. For each aspect, we detail the scope, methodology, data sources. This comprehensive examination aims to illuminate the nuances of infrastructure and awareness levels, shedding light on the prospects and obstacles within the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) context.

2.1 Aspect A: Infrastructure Landscape Analysis

Scope and Objectives

PIDs are fundamental for establishing a reliable and globally accessible research infrastructure. In the MENA region, where diverse research outputs contribute significantly to the global knowledge pool, the utilization of PIDs remains limited. The infrastructure landscape analysis aspect aims to address this gap by:

- Analyzing the current infrastructure landscape of repositories and publishing platforms in the MENA region.
- Assessing the awareness and adoption of PIDs within MENA repositories.
- Identifying gaps and challenges in PID adoption and awareness.
- Providing insights to promote open science policies and practices in the MENA region.

Methodology and Data Sources

We gathered data from standardized sources to obtain a comprehensive view of the MENA research infrastructure landscape:

- [Registry of Open Access Repositories \(ROAR\)](#)
- [Directory of Open Access Repositories \(OpenDOAR\)](#)
- [Confederation of Open Access Repositories \(COAR\)](#)
- [Registry of Research Data Repositories \(re3data.org\)](#)
- [Public Knowledge Project \(PKP\) Usage Data](#)
- [Dataverse Installations Data](#)
- [DSpace Installations Data](#)
- [DataCite Fabrica](#)

Rationale for Selection

These sources were chosen for their accuracy and coverage in the scholarly community. For example:

- ROAR and OpenDOAR are known for cataloging open access repositories globally.
- re3data.org provides insights into data-sharing practices.
- Usage data from Public Knowledge Project (PKP) installations offers insights into open access publishing platforms.
- Dataverse and DSpace installations provide information on data repositories.

Relevance to DataCite Global Access Program

The information gathered from these sources informs the DataCite Global Access Program's strategy to foster open and accessible research infrastructure in MENA. By analyzing the landscape and identifying gaps in PID adoption, DataCite aims to:

- Develop targeted initiatives for PID integration in MENA repositories.
- Enhance the global visibility of MENA research outputs.
- Facilitate collaborations among stakeholders to promote open science policies.

Covered Points

Within the infrastructure landscape analysis, we cover the following information and data for 20 countries in MENA:

- Number of repositories per country
- Service Providers (SP) per country
- MENA repositories Aggregators and Networks
- Number of Public Knowledge Project (PKP) installations (OJS, OMP, OPS)
- Current PID Systems in MENA region repositories

Data Collection

- The data was manually collected by checking each country against the selected sources.
- Raw data sheets were curated to fit report requirements.
- Data was processed and charts were produced to illustrate the infrastructure landscape in MENA.

This report serves as a step towards understanding and addressing challenges in adopting Open Science practices in MENA. By leveraging insights gained from the infrastructure and awareness landscape analysis, DataCite aims to contribute to establishing an interconnected global research community adhering to open and transparent principles, thereby fostering sustainable and accessible research infrastructure worldwide.

2.2 Aspect B: Infrastructure awareness landscape analysis

Scope and Objectives

Understanding the awareness levels and existing policies regarding PIDs, Open Research practices, and national open science policies is crucial for establishing a robust research infrastructure in the MENA region. This report aims to delve into the infrastructure awareness landscape by:

- Analyzing existing institutional policies among open access repositories across MENA.

- Investigating current DataCite memberships, usage and participation in the region.
- Providing insights into the current state of awareness regarding PIDs, open research practices, and national open science policies.

Methodology and Data Sources

We gathered data from a variety of reputable and standardized sources to ensure a comprehensive overview of infrastructure awareness in MENA:

- [Registry of Open Access Repositories MAP \(ROARMAP\)](#): This source provides valuable insights into existing institutional policies among open access repositories.
- [UNESCO Open Science Policies Portal](#)
- DataCite Fabica: Utilizing internal DataCite systems such as Fabica helps in understanding the DataCite Community in the region.

Furthermore, to capture a more nuanced understanding, we conducted manual searches and gathered information through interviews with community members. These interviews provided valuable firsthand insights into the current landscape of awareness regarding PIDs, open research practices, and national open science policies in MENA.

Rationale for Selection

The selected sources were chosen for their ability to provide comprehensive and reliable data on infrastructure awareness:

- ROARMAP: Offers insights into existing institutional policies, a crucial aspect of understanding the adoption of open research practices.
- UNESCO Open Science Policies: Gives an overview of the nationally implemented open research policies.
- DataCite Dashboard: Provides data on DataCite memberships and adoptions, essential for assessing the reach and impact of DataCite in MENA.
- DataCite Fabica: Internal systems like Fabica help in understanding the composition and activities of the DataCite Community in the region.

- Manual Searches and Interviews: These methods were employed to gather nuanced and firsthand information, ensuring a holistic view of awareness levels in MENA.

Covered Points

Within the infrastructure awareness landscape analysis, we explore the following points:

- Existing institutional policies among open access repositories across MENA.
- Current DataCite memberships and adoptions in the region.
- The DataCite Community in MENA, including board members and expert groups.

Data Collection

- Data from ROARMAP, DataCite Dashboard, and DataCite Fabica were analyzed to understand institutional policies, memberships, and the DataCite Community.
- Public information from www.datacite.org was utilized.
- Manual searches and interviews with community members provided additional insights.

This report's exploration of the infrastructure awareness landscape in MENA aims to illuminate the current state of awareness regarding PIDs, open research practices, and national open science policies.

Table 1: List of countries in the MENA region.

Country	
Algeria	Morocco
Bahrain	Oman
Egypt	Qatar
Iran	Saudi Arabia
Iraq	Palestine
Israel	Sudan
Jordan	Syria
Kuwait	Tunisia
Lebanon	United Arab Emirates
Libya	Yemen

3. Results and Discussions

Aspect A: Infrastructure Landscape Analysis in MENA

3.1 Existing Repositories & Systems in MENA

We collected information about the numbers of repositories, PKP products landscape (OJS, OPS), repositories aggregators and networks (COAR), and did a comparison between all data sources. We could not find any tracked installation for Open Preprint System (OPS) with PKP data in MENA countries.

According to ROAR, there are in total 94 repositories in MENA. The comparison of the number of repositories by country shows Algeria (16), Iran (16), Sudan (13), and Egypt (12) are the countries with the highest number of repositories, followed by Saudi Arabia (10) and Palestine (7). Also, we can see that almost 65% of MENA countries have few or no repositories at all discoverable within ROAR.

Figure 1: Repositories per Country, ROAR.

According to OpenDOAR, there are 108 repositories in MENA. The comparison of the number of repositories by country shows Algeria (22), Iran (17), Sudan (16), and Saudi Arabia (11) are the countries with the highest number of repositories, followed by Egypt (9), Palestine (8), and the United Arab Emirates (6). Also, we can see that almost 60% of MENA countries have low or no repositories at all discoverable within ROAR.

Figure 2: Repositories per Country, OpenDOAR.

According to re3data, there are 16 data repositories in MENA. The comparison of the number of repositories by country shows Israel (10) with the highest number of repositories, followed by Lebanon (2), Egypt (1), Tunisia (1), Saudi Arabia, and Sudan (1). Also, we can see that almost 70% of MENA countries have few or no repositories at all discoverable within re3data.

Figure 3: Repositories per Country, re3data.

In Table 2, we can see that Lebanon is the only country in the region that has Dataverse installations.

Table 2: Number of Dataverse installations in MENA. Source: Dataverse Installations Data.

Country	Number of Dataverse Installations
Lebanon	2

According to the DSpace registry, there are 134 repositories in MENA. The comparison of the number of repositories by country shows Sudan (26) with the highest number of repositories, followed by Algeria (16), Oman (16), Iran (12) and UAE (11). Also, we can see that almost 45% of MENA countries have few or no repositories at all discoverable within the DSpace Registry.

Figure 4: Repositories per Country, DSpace.

According to the OJS installation per country, there are 553 OJS installations in MENA. The comparison of the number of installations by country shows Iraq (136) with the highest number of installations, followed by Iran (88), Morocco (86), and Algeria (42).

Figure 5: Number of OJS Installations per Country, PKP Beacon Data.

According to the OMP installation per country, there are 9 OMP installations in MENA. The comparison of the number of installations by country shows Algeria (3) and Libya (3) with the highest number of installations, followed by Yemen, Saudi Arabia, and Iran with a single installation for each country.

Figure 6: Number of OMP Installations per Country, PKP Beacon Data.

Comparison Between all Data Sources

Although there are differences among the different sources for repositories per country in MENA, the comparison highlights some trends. Algeria is leading with the highest number of repositories in MENA followed by Iran, Sudan, and Saudi Arabia. Also, the figure shows that almost 35% of countries in MENA have very few or no repositories at all that are discoverable in these data sources.

Figure 7: Comparison Between Different Data Sources.

3.2 Repository Service Providers Landscape in MENA

Figure 8 shows that almost 53% of the discoverable repositories in ROAR are using DSpace and 20% of repositories are using EPrints.

Figure 8: Repositories Service Providers in MENA, ROAR.

Figure 9 shows that almost 66% of the discoverable repositories in OpenDOAR are using DSpace and 18% of repositories are using EPrints.

Figure 9: Repository Service Providers in MENA, OpenDOAR.

Figure 10 shows that according to the re3data registry, 60% of the discoverable repositories are using Other software and 20% each are using DSpace and Eprints.

Figure 10: Repository Service Providers in MENA, re3data.

Figure 11 shows that according to the re3data registry, 66.7% of the discoverable repositories in MENA are not integrated with any PID and only 16.7% are integrated with DOIs. This figure is a good representation of the low levels of awareness among the community about the value and importance of integrating PID in research workflows and repositories.

Figure 11: PID systems in MENA, re3data.

3.3 Infrastructure Landscape Discussions

The analysis of repository landscapes across the MENA region, as depicted in Figures 1 to 4, reveals significant disparities in repository availability and discoverability. Despite the region's rich scholarly outputs, a notable portion of MENA countries have few or no repositories discoverable within global aggregators and networks. However, countries such as Algeria, Iran, and Sudan have emerged as leaders in repository presence across multiple registries.

Among the observed repositories, a prevalent trend emerges in the adoption of open-source platforms, as evidenced by Figures 5 and 6. Iraq notably leads in the installation of (OJS), signifying a substantial interest in embracing open-access publishing platforms within the region. Similarly, the adoption of OMP installations, particularly notable in Algeria and Libya, reflects a growing interest in open scholarly communication practices.

Furthermore, DSpace emerges as the most widely adopted software for repositories in the MENA region, with notable usage in countries such as Sudan, Algeria, and Oman, as

indicated in Figure 4. This widespread adoption underscores the region's recognition of the importance of robust repository infrastructures in facilitating scholarly communication and knowledge dissemination.

Despite these promising developments, challenges persist in maximizing the visibility and impact of MENA research outputs. The prevalence of low repository visibility underscores the urgent need to raise awareness about the significance of repositories and their integration with persistent identifiers, such as DOIs. Enhancing repository discoverability not only amplifies the visibility of MENA research on the global stage but also fosters greater collaboration and knowledge exchange within the region and beyond.

In conclusion, while MENA countries exhibit varying degrees of engagement with repository infrastructures, concerted efforts are needed to address the disparities in repository visibility and adoption. By prioritizing awareness-raising initiatives and leveraging open-access platforms, the MENA region can harness its scholarly potential to contribute meaningfully to the global research landscape while fostering a culture of openness and collaboration.

Aspect B: Awareness Landscape Analysis in MENA

3.4 Landscape of Open Access Repositories Institutional Policies (Source: ROARMAP)

The total number of mandatory archiving policies in MENA countries according to data from the Registry of Open Access Repositories Mandatory Archiving Policies (ROARMAP). Algeria has 3 policies followed by Iran, Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, and Palestine with one policy for each country. 75% of countries in MENA are lacking these mandatory archiving policies among their Open Access repositories or not registering them in ROARMAP.

Figure 12: The number of policies per country in MENA, ROARMAP.

3.5 Awareness Landscape Discussions

In assessing the awareness landscape surrounding open access repositories and persistent identifiers (PIDs) in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, several key findings emerge from the analysis of existing policies, DataCite memberships, and community engagement efforts.

The examination of mandatory archiving policies, as documented in the Registry of Open Access Repositories Mandatory Archiving Policies (ROARMAP), reveals a notable disparity in policy adoption among MENA countries. While Algeria stands out with three policies, followed by Iran, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and Palestine with one policy each, a staggering 75% of countries in MENA lack these mandatory archiving policies for their open access repositories or have not registered them in ROARMAP. This underscores the urgent need for concerted efforts to promote policy development and implementation across the region to ensure the long-term preservation and accessibility of research outputs.

Moreover, Figure 12 illustrates the distribution of DataCite Findable DOIs as of October 2023, further emphasizing the contributions of leading organizations such as CNRST, IISKS Consortium, and KAUST. Within the DataCite community, the MENA region is currently represented by one member on the DataCite Executive Board and three members in the EMEA Expert Group.

Table 5 highlights the names, organizations, and countries of DataCite EMEA Expert Group members from the MENA region, showcasing the diverse expertise and contributions of individuals from Qatar, Jordan, and Algeria. This diverse representation underscores the region's potential to contribute meaningfully to global discussions on persistent identifier systems and open science practices.

In light of these findings, it is evident that there is a significant need for various community engagement efforts, including outreach activities, technical training, and funding opportunities, to raise awareness and foster greater adoption of open access repositories and persistent identifiers in the MENA region. By addressing these gaps and building capacity within the regional research community, MENA countries can actively contribute to the advancement of open science principles and maximize the visibility and impact of their research outputs on the global stage.

4. Conclusion

PIDs have gained prominence as a crucial component of research infrastructure and workflows. They offer a standardized way to identify and locate research outputs, enabling seamless navigation through the vast landscape of scholarly content and enhancing the discoverability of research. However, despite the growing prominence of open research and the pivotal role of PIDs and DOIs in scholarly communication, the number of repositories in MENA that are discoverable in global aggregates and networks remains considerably low. Moreover, the awareness of the value of DOIs in MENA is low, which is clear in the DOI adoption level across the region. This gap in adoption poses a significant challenge to the integration of MENA research outputs into the global scholarly ecosystem, limiting the region's visibility and contribution to the broader scientific community.

To address these pressing challenges, concerted engagement and outreach efforts are imperative among various stakeholders, including academic institutions, funding agencies, service providers, librarians, and research communities. Raising awareness

about the benefits of open science policies and advocating for the widespread adoption of PIDs, particularly DOIs, will be crucial in fostering a more inclusive and interconnected research landscape in MENA. Such endeavors will not only elevate the visibility and impact of MENA research but also contribute to the advancement of global scientific knowledge and collaboration, ultimately fostering a more robust and comprehensive understanding of complex societal challenges and opportunities.

5. Funding Statement

This report is part of DataCite Global Access Program ([GAP](#)) activities. The program has been made possible in part by grant 2022-316573 from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative.

6. Acknowledgments

Special thanks to all the data sources and the repository aggregators/networks for making their data open and up to date.

7. Appendix: Glossary

MENA: Middle East and North Africa
PID: Persistent Identifier
DOI: Digital Object Identifier
SP: Service Provider
GAP: Global Access Program
GAF: Global Access Fund
CZI: Chan Zuckerberg Initiative
ROAR: Registry of Open Access Repositories
OpenDOAR: Directory of Open Access Repositories
COAR: Confederation of Open Access Repositories
Re3data: Registry of Research Data Repositories
ROARMAP: Registry of Open Access Repositories Mandatory Archiving Policies
PKP: Public Knowledge Project
OJS: Open Journal Systems
OMP: Open Monograph Press
OPS: Open Preprint Systems

8. References

[1] "Bolstering open science infrastructures for all," UNESCO, Nov. 2022.

<https://doi.org/10.54677/QZPQ1991>

[2] Open Science Infrastructure. [Wikipedia]. Available from:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_Science_Infrastructure [Accessed 29 March 2024]

[3] Meadows, A., Haak, L., Brown, J. (2019) Persistent Identifiers: The Building Blocks of the Research Information Infrastructure. Insights 32 (1): 9. DOI:

<http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.457>

[4] Brown J, Jones P, Meadows A, Murphy F, Clayton P. UK PID consortium: cost-benefit analysis. Zenodo; 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4772627>

[5] Meadows A, Haak L. How persistent identifiers can save scientists time. FEMS Microbiol Lett. 2018; 365 (15). <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsle/fny143>

[6] Buys M. DataCite vision to reality | 2022-2025 strategic plan. DataCite; 2022.

<https://doi.org/10.14454/79cy-qe15>

[7] Mejias G, Cousijn H. DataCite launches Global Access Program with support from CZI. DataCite; 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5438/3GS5-3J26>

[8] Mejias G, Cousijn H. Announcing the First Cohort of DataCite Global Access Fund Awardees! DataCite; 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5438/XR20-PJ13>

[9] Hendricks G, Buys M. Working for global equity through Digital Object Identifiers. Upstream; 2023. <https://doi.org/10.54900/6sz4q-47185>